

Use of E-Learning and Web Technologies in Enhancing the Curriculum of a New Computer Security Unit¹

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Abstract: This paper provides a case study in the development of a new computer security unit as part of a number of different final year undergraduate courses including computer science, software engineering and digital forensics. The study also comprises the enhancement of the curriculum of the new unit using e-learning and Web-based technologies and tools. The case study demonstrates some areas of success, such as the specialized usage of Cloud-based technologies and tools with a focus on computer security concepts. It also highlights some limitations of generic virtual learning environments when tackling a diverse topic and a diverse group of students. The paper touches on the challenges encountered and the adopted solutions and provides some measure for the student satisfaction with the new experience. We also discuss the future opportunities and threats inherent to the adopted approach.

Keywords: Computer security, computer education, curriculum enhancement, e-learning, teaching cases

Introduction

This case study is centered on a new third year undergraduate unit, called Secure Systems (COMSEC), which started running for the first time in the first semester of 2011/2012 and as part of the Digital Forensics (DF), Software Engineering (SE) and Computer Science (CS) undergraduate courses in the School of Computing, University of Portsmouth, UK. Computer and information security is rapidly rising to the top of the list of the most important issues in the IT industry and the global market due to the vast opportunities and threats enabled by the technological advances in computing systems. According to a recent report by the Global Industry Analysis (GIA) [GIALink] the size of the cyber security market is to reach \$80 Billion in 2017, and currently cyber crime costs the world economy a staggering \$1 Trillion. The pressures from industry mandate an approach to computer security education, which is flexible, informative and effective in building up the knowledge and skills students need when starting their professional career after university. Hence, many Higher Education (HE) institutions have responded to such need by starting new courses (and enhancing exiting ones) in computer and information security, digital forensics and other relevant areas. COMSEC, being one such course, was started in response to the School's call for a new strategic educational direction to respond to the needs from industry highlighted above.

The size of the class in the current academic year, 2011/2012, was 28 students. However, it is envisaged that this number will increase to around 100 students in the following years as a result of

¹ This study was conducted in the 2011/2012 academic year while at the School of Computing, University of Portsmouth. Please note, by this time, it is likely that many of the Web links referenced in the paper will be broken.

the changes to the structure of courses in the School of Computing from 2012 onwards. These changes will see COMSEC become a core rather than an optional part of the curriculum for both the CS and SE groups. Currently, it is only core in the DF course curriculum, and optional for the CS and SE groups.

COMSEC had two main Learning Outcomes (LOs):

1. to allow the students to explain and evaluate models, techniques and mechanisms for securing computer systems, and
2. to design security solutions for computer systems to protect sensitive information

The content driven from these LOs was developed to cover a wide range of technical security topics without delving too much in any one individual topic. The basic topics covered therefore included authentication mechanisms and protocols, authorization architectures, access control models, security policies and languages, network security concepts and finally, threat analysis and threat trees.

In designing the teaching strategy for COMSEC, we had a well-established learning model in mind from the beginning, namely Kolb's model [KOLB1975]. This model defines learning as a process that leads to the generation of knowledge, where the process consists of four stages in its most basic form:

- *Concrete experience*: where the learner learns by actually doing something related to the topic being taught or having an experience that allows the learner to reason on the topic. Such experience was provided in the form of the COMSEC tutorial and practical sessions.
- *Reflective observation*: here the learner is required to observe an experience or to reflect upon some experience they have had in the past to learn from it. Formal lectures provided the time for reflective observation of the practical experience provided by in the tutorials.
- *Abstract conceptualisation*: where the learner concludes and learns from the experience thus focusing on the abstract aspect of it. Out of the tutorial and lectures sessions, the students used off-class time spent in self-study and research to make abstract conclusions on what they learnt.
- *Active Experimentation*: finally, at this stage, the learner plans again a new experience feeding into the knowledge they have learnt from the previous experiences. The knowledge that the students formed in all the previous stages was then used to feed into the COMSEC coursework as a ground for new experimentation. The main requirement for such a learning phase is that the coursework must build on knowledge gained in material supporting the previous learning phases.

Literature provides a plethora of teaching and learning models such as Keller's ARCS model of motivational design [KELL1987], Maslow's hierarchy of needs [MAS1943], the ADDIE model of systematic instructional design [ADD1996], Reigeluth Elaboration Theory [REIG1999] and many others. The main reason for choosing Kolb's model was that it had been adopted in previous years in developing the curriculum of other units related to the DF course demonstrating excellent student learning experiences.

In the rest of the paper, we shall first outline the main challenges that faced us when first considering the development of the curriculum and its enhancement. Then we define the various aspects of the solution related to the use of e-learning and Web technologies and tools that was adopted. We then provide an overview of the feedback we obtained from the students and peer tutors in the unit on the enhancement and its areas of strengths and weaknesses. Finally, we provide a more in-depth discussion of these results in light of future enhancements.

The Challenge

Since the unit underlying the case study was run for the first time, the general context of the case study is the development of new content that suits the requirements of the courses (i.e. DF, SE and CS) of which the unit is part. Like any other new unit dealing with a rich area of knowledge, this content is not invented but is rather based on a well-established body of literature and research. Similarly, enhancement in this context takes the form of the use of innovative approaches, in this case e-Learning, in achieving the learning outcomes of the unit.

In most computer security and cryptography courses the traditional approach based on passive lectures “*dominates the current teaching of information system security*” [YUR2001]. While cryptography [RUB1997] and systems focused [OTH2009] teaching provide mathematical and hands-on skills, respectively, the aim of the COMSEC unit was to provide a survey breadth course that aims at equipping students with the necessary fundamental knowledge robust to advances in security technologies while at the same time, maintain a reasonable level of practical training.

One of the main challenges in teaching a survey breadth computer security unit like COMSEC is the diversity of topics involved, which cover wide disciplines of computer science, logic and mathematics, software engineering, social and legal engineering and risk and economic management of security. In addition, the challenge in this case becomes multi-dimensional given the diversity of the students’ background. The students attending the unit belonged to three different areas: computer science, software engineering and digital forensics. Each of these groups has traditionally a different approach to learning, with the computer science students focused on learning by hands-on programming and software development with some knowledge of the software engineering process. On the other hand, the software engineering students focus more on learning by literature research and the use of tools on the general processes of system design and development. Finally, digital forensic students focus on a mixture of learning approaches involving literature research on socio-legal aspects of computer forensics and the hands-on usage (rather than development) of software tools related to narrow and specific problems in computer forensics.

Another challenge was the novelty of the subject to the current group of students attending the COMSEC unit. The majority of the students demonstrated very little knowledge and limited exposure to the fundamental concepts of computer and information security. This was evident through the results of a diagnosis test conducted at the beginning of the unit (See the section on Student Feedback).

Therefore, any curriculum enhancement in this case needed to be considered in light of the above multi-dimensional nature of diversity in COMSEC. In order to tackle these variations in learning styles and course cultures, the main solution of adopting e-Learning and Web technologies and tools was introduced as an enhancement of the curriculum of the new unit in relation to existing approaches in teaching computer security [JAMES1999,YUR2001,CAR2004].

In literature, there are many examples of the use of e-Learning technologies and tools in teaching computer security such as [COGO2003,JORD2011]. The Web also provides free tools such as Bob’s Business Information Security e-Learning [BobLink] tool aimed at non-security audiences. In particular an attractive emergent area is Cloud systems, offering new directions for both teaching and learning, which facilitate sharing of information, simulation of computer security concepts and a peer-to-peer model of learning.

The Solution

From the challenges outlined in the previous section, we found that teaching a diverse group of students a diverse topic such as computer security is not an easy task, and hence, it requires a methodology and the use of common and flexible techniques to maximize the students' learning experience. As a result, we decided to adopt a traditional teaching methodology enhanced with e-learning technologies as a common ground for enhancing the computer security curriculum. The definition of e-learning adopted is based on the definition given by the Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC) in that it is "*learning facilitated and supported through the use of information and communications technology*" [JISCLink].

Literature supports our belief that e-learning and technology-based learning is beneficial to the teaching and learning process. This has been highlighted in as early as the work of Blumenfeld et al. [BLUM1991] who identified a number of benefits that technology (including e-Learning) can bring to student learning. These included enhancing interest and motivation, providing access to information, allowing active, manipulable representations, structuring the process with tactical and strategic support, diagnosing and correcting errors and managing complexity and aiding production. Similarly, [GOV2001] highlights several advantages of an e-learning pedagogy in aspects such as content development, storage, packaging and management of content, student support and assessment. However, e-learning also brings some disadvantages, such as the cost of the material/programs, familiarity with technology and the social acceptance and readiness of the learners [NED2008].

Since technology-based learning is best when demonstrating concrete examples, we therefore adopted this type of enhancement during two of the above phases in Kolb's model; namely the *concrete experience* and *active experimentation* phases. In following this approach, we relied on some of the priorities and objectives highlighted by the University's Learning, Teaching and Assessment Strategy document [LTASLink] in guiding the development and implementation of the solution adopted in COMSEC. These specifically include the priority to "*continue to embed and extend e-learning, e-assessment and e-support within the core curriculum*" and the objectives of the "*Delivery of a flexible, accessible, engaging, responsive and relevant curriculum*" as well as promoting a curriculum that encourages students to "*develop independent and reflective learning, critical thinking and problem solving skills*", which is a vital objective when teaching computer security due to the hard nature of the real-world security problems that demand such skills of the involved professionals.

We now discuss in brief detail the individual components of this enhancement.

Use of Web and Cloud Technologies

The first component of the curriculum enhancement solution was in the form of adopting Web and Cloud technologies in enhancing the students learning experience of certain security-related concepts. This solution had two main components:

- The use of SkyDrive [SDLink] a Web-based storage Cloud that provides accessible storage of files and some access control capabilities, as a public directory for storing public keys of students needed in learning authentication protocols. SkyDrive was also used as a message communication medium that a network attacker can use to generate knowledge from agent communications. Finally, the access rights in SkyDrive accounts were used to demonstrate how access control models work in protecting the security of digital assets.

The second type of Cloud used was a social network, in particular Facebook [FBLink]. Facebook's access control model was also used to demonstrate access control concepts in social networking sites when protecting publicly vulnerable digital information.

Use of Computer-based Tools Obtained from the Internet

The second element of the solution was to use free tools available to download from the Internet and which matched the intended enhancement of the curriculum. There were two tools used:

- A Java-based XACML editor, the UMU XACML Editor [UXLink], was used by the students to learn how to construct security policies expressed in the XACML standard [XACML2005]. UMU's XACML editor is freely available to download from [UXLink], therefore it was accessible to students during their off-class study time and coursework preparation.

The second tool was the OpenSSL [OSSLink] package, which is part of many standard Linux distributions. OpenSSL provides a user API that implements several cryptographic and key distribution and management operations necessary to demonstrate key security concepts related to authentication of agents and secure network communications.

Virtual Learning Environments

Victory [VICLink], the University of Portsmouth's Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), was explored in COMSEC for encouraging virtual student discussions of the various topics covered in the lectures as well as to provide off-class access to the learning material, lectures and tutorials delivered in the unit. Additionally, Victory was also used as a learning platform encompassing all the lectures and tutorials material delivered during the classes and lab sessions. Finally, Victory was used to provide feedback to students on their tutorial and lab exercises.

Alignment of Teaching, Student Support and Assessment

The proposed solution above was also designed and implemented with the appropriate alignment of all main aspects of the curriculum in mind, namely teaching, student support and assessment [LTASLink]. Figure 1 below demonstrates the various relationships of this alignment for the case of the COMSEC curriculum enhancement.

Figure 1: Alignment of the Teaching, Student Support and Assessment Aspects of the E-learning Curriculum Enhancement in COMSEC

As clear from the figure, teaching and student support in COMSEC were coordinated together in terms of making sure that the learning outcome tackled during the teaching sessions were matched with the appropriate level of practical and tutorial support. Formal teaching was aligned with the assessment in that the knowledge developed during lectures feed into the assessment by means of the

coursework. Finally, student support also was used to support the performance of students while they tackled their coursework assignments.

Evaluation of the Effects of the Enhancement

Since this was the first time that COMSEC was running, there were no results from previous years to compare to and therefore it is hard to demonstrate an *enhancement* over some existing related approach. Therefore, we first start by ensuring that the quantitative results of the learning experience were within the expected norm in the Computing courses at the University. The following Table 1 provides a summary of the distribution of the final marks for the students' assessment in COMSEC for the academic year 2011/2012.

Mark Category	Number of Students
70-79	4
60-69	5
50-59	7
40-49	10
30-39	0
20-29	1
<20	1
Students Total Number	28
Average Mark	52%

Table 1: COMSEC Final Results Distribution

This distribution shows a performance within the expected average of the School of Computing, which is between 40% and 60%, thus demonstrating that LOs (including the effect of the curriculum enhancement) were assessed to be within the expected norm.

As a qualitative evaluation of the curriculum and the effect of the enhancement, various aspects of the unit were evaluated through the various feedbacks obtained from the students and from other staff members involved in teaching the unit. We discuss in the following paragraphs the results of such feedbacks.

Student Feedback

Student feedback was obtained over three main points in the duration of COMSEC. The duration was the length of a semester, 12 weeks. The feedback was obtained at the beginning of the unit on Week 1, at the middle points around Weeks 5/7, and at the end of the unit in Weeks 11/12.

Feedback at the beginning of the unit:

This feedback was taken in the form of a diagnosis test to obtain some idea of the level of the students' knowledge, experience and understanding of key computer security concepts, including security properties, authentication protocols, security policies, network security, cryptography and public-key infrastructures. The number of students who undertook the test was 28, i.e. the full class. At this stage, about 25 students (approximately 90%) demonstrated some lack of knowledge and misunderstanding in most of the above computer security concepts covered by COMSEC's LOs and

content. This was an expected result since none of the courses to which COMSEC belongs provides any formal security education in earlier years.

Additionally, discussion lists were set-up early during the unit around Week 3 on Victory for students as well as the tutors to discuss various aspects of the lectures and tutorials.

Feedback at points in the middle of the unit:

This form of student feedback was obtained via several means. We briefly review these next.

- At Week 5 of the semester, another round of students' feedback was obtained through an "early bird feedback" form. The questions were based on the "Stop/Start/Change" style. These included asking the students about:
 - Things they wanted to stop happening
 - Things they wanted to start happening
 - Things they wanted to see changed

In this case, the three questions were directed at both categories of teaching, the theoretical in the form of lectures, and the practical in the form of tutorials/lab sessions. The response rate was low (about 18%, 5 students), and generally did not include any insightful comments on the e-learning approach. It was however clear that 4 out of the 5 responses did indicate that solutions were needed for the tutorials and/or some guidance. As a result, we utilized the e-learning and Web technologies in providing some of this guidance as described in the previous section. We believe that the low rate of response is indicative of the lack of interest when feedback is sought through general means, such as the "Stop/Start/Change" method.

- In addition to the above formal means of obtaining student feedback, meetings with individual students were also used to obtain informal feedback on various learning and teaching aspects of the lectures and the tutorials. As a result, these meetings helped the lecturer clarify to the students a few misunderstandings of the technical aspects of the material taught and the technical tools used in teaching, and provided better view of the learning curve for the students.

Feedback at the end of the unit:

The final form of feedback was obtained via two means:

- The first form of final feedback was the formal unit feedback questionnaires that are provided by the University on all its units. This questionnaire is a standard one containing the following questions:
 - What was the best part of the unit?
 - Aspect/aspects I had problems with:
 - I would have liked more:
 - I would have liked less:
 - Any other general comments on the unit:

As can be seen, these questions are pretty general and do not directly tackle any specific aspect of the unit. Nonetheless, of the 13 responses to the feedback request, 7 of them (more than 50%) indicated that the best part of COMSEC was the learning experience centered on authentication protocols, which was mainly driven by the SkyDrive Cloud environment. The general measure of satisfaction mean level obtained from this feedback was 3.87/5.00, which is higher than the School's acceptable minimum level of 3.75/5.00.

- The second form of the final feedback was specifically designed to measure how useful was the COMSEC curriculum enhancement (in the form of introducing e-learning and Web technologies) to the students in improving their security knowledge and skills. The questionnaire itself was designed using Google Docs and is available from [GDOCLink]. In the following section, we discuss the outcome of this questionnaire.

Curriculum Enhancement Results

The e-learning questionnaire was proposed to the COMSEC class towards the end of the semester. Of the total 28 students, only 7 replied, which represents a percentage of 25%. Nonetheless, one can get some sense of the general satisfaction and feeling of the students in relation to the e-learning-based curriculum enhancement implemented in COMSEC.

The first question was to check whether the respondents had been attending the tutorials, which were the centre focus of the curriculum enhancement. As indicated by the answers of Table 2, all of these had attended some if not all of the tutorials.

Table 2: Attendance Behaviour in COMSEC’s Tutorials

In general, as concluded from Q10 shown in Table 3 below, majority of responses indicated satisfaction with the use of software and Web/Cloud technologies.

Table 3: Satisfaction Level of Software and Web Technologies Used in COMSEC

Only one student had a neutral opinion and one student thought that these technologies were not useful at all. Furthermore, we found that 6 students preferred a technology-based curriculum as opposed to only one who preferred a theory-based one, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Technology versus Theory Preferences in COMSEC

And in addition, some of them thought this should be the style to adopt in the future. For example, when asked in the questionnaire “Which other technologies would you suggest to include in future versions of this unit? Include any software, Web services, online tools or any e-Learning technology you think should have been used”. The answers included:

“Blog especially for ComSec , every lecture/tutorial should be online after finishing it and allow students to share their ideas/knowledge in a more friendly environment ...” and,

“Maybe some kind of network simulator to visually model an attack? It’s hard to model an attack across multiple machines on only your own computer”.

In general, these results (coupled with the unit’s coursework results) indicate that the enhancement was successful and it had a positive effect. Next, we discuss in more detail the outcome of the students’ satisfaction with the individual components of the curriculum enhancement.

Results of the Use of Web and Cloud Technologies:

From the response to the questionnaire in Questions 2 and 3, as shown in Table 5 below, it was clear that the majority of responses found that SkyDrive storage Cloud was helpful in enhancing the learning experience mostly related to the topic of authentication protocols and mechanisms.

<p>Q2: The use of SkyDrive storage cloud has helped me in enhancing my learning experience of security overall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strongly Agree • Agree • Disagree • Strongly Disagree • No Opinion 	<table border="1"> <caption>Data for Q2 Chart</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>No Opinion</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Count	Strongly Agree	0	Agree	5	Disagree	2	Strongly Disagree	0	No Opinion	0
Response	Count												
Strongly Agree	0												
Agree	5												
Disagree	2												
Strongly Disagree	0												
No Opinion	0												
<p>Q3: Which of these concepts did you better understand as a result of using SkyDrive?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentication mechanisms • Authentication protocols • Dolev-Yao Attackers • All of the above • None of the above 	<table border="1"> <caption>Data for Q3 Chart</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Concept</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Authentication mechanisms</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Authentication protocols</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dolev-Yao Attackers</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>All of the above</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>None of the above</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Concept	Count	Authentication mechanisms	5	Authentication protocols	2	Dolev-Yao Attackers	0	All of the above	1	None of the above	2
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Table 5: Usefulness of the SkyDrive Cloud Environment and its Usage in COMSEC

We found that these results were satisfactory given that SkyDrive is a generic Cloud and does not provide generally any specific aspects relevant to the teaching of computer security concepts. One explanation lies in the manner that SkyDrive was used, namely in a specialized way to explain the security concepts of authentication protocols and network attack models.

Results of the Use of Computer-based Tools:

The introduction of the UMU XACML editor and the OpenSSL package to the unit had a very positive response among the students, with all of the respondents agreeing that OpenSSL was useful in one way or another, as shown in Table 6 below.

<p>Q4: I found the use of OpenSSL useful in enhancing my learning of security during the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tutorials • Coursework • Out-of-contact learning activities • All of the above • None of the above 	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Tutorials</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Coursework</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Out-of-contact learning activities</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>All of the above</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>None of the above</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Category	Count	Tutorials	5	Coursework	4	Out-of-contact learning activities	1	All of the above	1	None of the above	0		
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<p>Q5: OpenSSL helped me in understanding:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentication mechanisms • Authentication protocols • Dolev-Yao attackers • IPSec • All of the above • None of the above 	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Authentication mechanisms</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Authentication protocols</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dolev-Yao attackers</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>IPSec</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>All of the above</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>None of the above</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Category	Count	Authentication mechanisms	5	Authentication protocols	4	Dolev-Yao attackers	1	IPSec	3	All of the above	1	None of the above	0
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Table 6: Usefulness of OpenSSL and its Usage in COMSEC

Five students also agreed that UMU XACML editor was a useful tool, as shown in Table 7 below.

<p>Q6: How easy did you find the use of the XACML editor?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very easy • Easy • Normal • Difficult • Very Difficult 	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Very easy</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Easy</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Normal</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Difficult</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Very Difficult</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Category	Count	Very easy	0	Easy	1	Normal	5	Difficult	1	Very Difficult	0
Category	Count												
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Easy	1												
Normal	5												
Difficult	1												
Very Difficult	0												
<p>Q7: I found the use of the XACML editor useful in enhancing my learning experience in the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tutorials • Coursework • Out-of-contact learning activities • All of the above • None of the above 	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Tutorials</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Coursework</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Out-of-contact learning activities</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>All of the above</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>None of the above</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Category	Count	Tutorials	4	Coursework	2	Out-of-contact learning activities	0	All of the above	0	None of the above	2
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Table 7: Usefulness of the UMU XACML Editor tool and its Usage in COMSEC

In our opinion, this is due to the specialized nature of these tools, which makes them close to the learning outcomes of a unit like COMSEC. One student only thought that the UMU XACML editor was difficult to use, however this is a user interface problem of the tool, rather than a problem of the tool's functionality itself.

Results of the Use of VLEs

As one can see from the results of the question on the virtual learning environment, Victory, shown in Table 8 below, 5 of the responses thought that Victory was a waste of time or of no use and these in addition had either rarely or never used Victory blogs.

Table 8: Usefulness of the University's VLE, Victory, in COMSEC

As a result, the response/usage rate of the COMSEC Victory-based discussion lists was low as shown from the outcome of the question in Table 9.

Table 9: Usage Rate of the University's VLE, Victory, during COMSEC

On the other hand, the contrasting student opinion when comparing Victory to the use of SkyDrive (Table 5) leads one to conclude that negative opinion on Victory combined with its usage patterns is in line with the general shared dissatisfaction of the majority of the student body in the University of Portsmouth with Victory. The consequence of this has recently led the University to the adoption of Moodle [MLink] as its future VLE for all its units.

Peer Feedback

Peer feedback was obtained from other members of staff who were involved in the tutoring of the COMSEC practical sessions. Their input was mainly of technical nature involving advice on the modification of certain tutorial exercises to be in line with the level of the students attending their sessions. They also suggested the introduction of new *social learning techniques*. Social learning techniques involve enhancing the students' learning experience through the use of Web social networking, mainly in this case the use of Facebook, to aid the understanding of computer security as well as encourage mutual learning via means popular with the students. Therefore, the COMSEC Facebook page was started in response to this feedback [FBSLink].

However, as one can infer from the usage rate of the page, this solution did not prove to be successful as few students only interacted with the page and none of them actually used it to convey any useful learning material and ideas. Our view is that such social solutions must come from the student groups themselves and cannot be imposed on them, if the change is to have a positive effect on the learning experience.

Nonetheless, a better more security-relevant usage of Facebook was related to Facebook's model of enforcing access control policies to demonstrate how authorization architectures and security policies work. This was used as an example in teaching the material in one the unit's tutorial sessions and also featured as an exercise in the coursework. It was another example of specialized usage of generic technology to demonstrate concepts relevant to the curriculum.

Feedback from the Unit Assessment Board (UAB)

The feedback from the UAB was positive both from the head of the School and the external examiner, who both indicated that COMSEC was run successfully and with excellent outcome. No specific comments were provided related to the curriculum enhancement for COMSEC.

Discussion

The experience of starting a new unit brings many challenges as we highlighted in previous sections and provides a learning experience for both the students and the lecturers/tutors. We consider that there were some elements of success in developing and enhancing COMSEC and some other elements that could have been done differently given the right conditions.

The key points of success that can be clearly identified both from the coursework final results and the students' feedback are:

- The specialized use of Cloud environments (mainly SkyDrive) helped the students in understanding better security concepts related to authentication protocols. This also builds on the fact that the current group was quite diverse belonging to several different undergraduate courses. The final results for student coursework indicated that Task 1 on authentication protocols was the task with the highest average mark of approximately 24/30 marks. Therefore we shall continue to utilize Cloud environments in future versions of the unit as appropriate.
- The use of specialized tools, such as the UMU XACML policy editor, freely available to download from the Web, helped the students in automating as well as appreciating the benefits of automatic policy editing, especially in the context of complex industrial-like environments where XACML is a standard used to specify complex security policies. Again, the students' performance in the coursework task related to XACML specification was excellent with an average of 22/30 marks.

On the other hand, there were points related to the curriculum enhancement that could have been improved or done differently:

- Building up small sub-groups of students, centered on a common problem, such as a mini group project, could have improved the usage rate of Victory's discussion lists and the social networking technologies such as COMSEC's Facebook environment. The lesson to be learnt here is that simply making a learning solution or environment available to students does not necessarily imply that they will embrace that solution or environment. In many cases, it is the common problem that drives the common adoption of solutions. Some reading of group learning theories and practice, e.g. [JAC2007] could have possibly improved the group's attitude to Victory and Facebook in the context of COMSEC. This point will form the focus of future enhancements in COMSEC.
- As it proved, the use of specialized educational tools such as the XACML editing tool is highly advantageous over the generic use of generic tools and environments such as Victory's VLE. The arrival of new generation of active learning tools in computer security courses, such as Cyber CIEGE [CYSLink][CONE2007][THOM2011], Tele-Lab [WILL2010] and CounterMeasures [JORD2011], may be considered in the future to maximize the students' learning outcome in a complex topic such as computer security.

We next discuss a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) analysis of the curriculum enhancement of the COMSEC unit.

Strengths

The e-learning enhancement of COMSEC curriculum followed a pedagogical approach based on traditional instructional design [HER2004], which is curriculum-focused developed by a centralized educational entity, in this case the lecturer. This approach was combined with social constructivism [VYG1978], involving the use of discussion forums and blogs by the students within COMSEC's VLE.

The main strengths of the enhancement using e-learning and Web technologies may be summarized as follows:

- More flexibility for the students to access and experiment with the material of the tutorials such that the students can enhance their understanding of the key security concepts delivered in COMSEC's lectures and perform experiments outside of the contact hours with the COMSEC lectures and tutorials. This advantage of the curriculum was facilitated by the use of Cloud and Web technologies.
- The Victory VLE provided a platform for students to share their ideas and solutions of the various aspects of COMSEC's technical material and coursework. This has the advantage of promoting shared communication based on specific goals in the learning process. More targeted utilization of this platform in the future can improve its usage rate through a problem-driven learning approach.
- VLEs also provide a medium for the lecturer to provide feedback on tutorials and practical exercises such that these are accessible at all time to the students to reflect upon, particularly in relation to their future learning activities. Therefore, Victory was used extensively by the lecturer/tutors to provided solutions of COMSEC's tutorial exercises and other off-class learning material related to the coursework.

Weaknesses

The lack of specialization of any of the e-learning solutions in the areas related to computer security education meant that either the usage of the environment or tool needed to be adapted to demonstrate computer security concepts, or altogether neglected by the students. For example, the lack of availability in the School of an online computer security-teaching environment meant that SkyDrive needed to be presented to and used differently by students to enhance their understanding of authentication protocols and modes of network attacks.

Opportunities and Constraints

The e-learning and Web technology-based enhancement in COMSEC, like in most other cases, is constrained by the scope of the demonstration factor in the learning experience. Such tools are useful in achieving learning-by-example or hands-on learning. However, they remain of limited use when formal teaching of theoretical computer security concepts is involved, where more traditional means of theory-driven methods are needed to provide the students with a strong time-proof theoretical background in "the science of computer security".

As a consequence, one local constraint related to students' diversity was the relevance of the approach to one specific group, namely DF group, who are more familiar than the other two groups (CS and SE) with using technical tools in learning due to the nature of their course. Therefore, we found that DF students were most active initially in interacting with the tools than the other two groups. Nonetheless, we envisage that the current experience learnt from the development and enhancement of COMSEC will be useful in enhancing existing diversified units and developing new ones in the future.

Threats

Despite the fact that computer security in terms of the COMSEC unit was a new area of education that the School of Computing adopted recently, there is no shortage of computer security-related courses out in the market and in the HE sector, many of which are in fact based on e-learning and Web technologies, some of which have moved to the next generation tools based on Web games (e.g. CyberCIEGE and CounterMeasures). Hence, the major threat to this enhancement is advances in the learning technologies outside of those available to the School, which may render the educational experience of students in the future lagging behind their peers elsewhere. Also, the very evolving nature of computer security in line with advances in computing and IT technologies implies that the use of general e-learning tools may fall behind the expressivity levels and subtlety of security attacks and vulnerabilities as well as their countermeasures.

To mitigate against these threats, one needs to invest in up-to-date technologies and enhance the staff expertise in the area of computer security in line with the state-of-the-art literature, in order to provide the students with the expected educational experience. Advanced research activities and formal technical training and certification are some of the other effective means of mitigation against these threats.

Conclusion and Future Work

This paper presented a case study in the development and enhancement of the curriculum for a new computer security unit along with a quantitative and qualitative measurement of the students experience in relation to this new unit. The main structure of the unit followed a classical lecture/tutorial/practical approach. e-Learning and Web technologies and tools were used to enhance the tutorials and practical sessions as well as aid the students in accomplishing the coursework assignments. According to the results of the student feedback, the enhancement demonstrated a positive outcome and experience for the students in relation to the use of specialized tools. On the other hand, general learning environments, such as the Victory VLE, were deemed to be less useful due to their lack of focus.

The development of COMSEC has provided the author with knowledge and confidence in the use of e-Learning and Web technologies and tools in teaching a complex subject such as computer security. This added self-awareness also extended to the improvement of the author's understanding of the various approaches that technologies can be used in dealing with diverse groups belonging to different course each with their own style of learning. One such new approach has been in the specialized usage of generic tools to target specific groups of learners.

Future directions for this work will involve the application of enhanced methods to future versions of the unit based on the current experience and the identification of new opportunities in applying the experience to other areas.

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